

TRIALS AND FICTION: A STUDY OF UPAMANYU CHATTERJEE'S THE REVENGE OF
THE NON-VEGETARIAN

Dr. K. Rekha, Lecturer in English, GDC (A) Ananthapuram. Ananthapuram District, Andhra Pradesh.

P. Nagarjuna, Research Scholar (Part time), Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur, AP and Lecturer in English, GDC (A) Ananthapuram. Ananthapuram District, Andhra Pradesh.

Abstract

The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian, Upamanyu Chatterjee's seventh book and 2018 publication, is a novella that explores the problems of modern India, including class divides, moral prejudices against meat, and the sluggishness of the judicial system. The novella's short, linear plot centres on a family of six who perished in a fire in Batia, Narmada Pradesh, along with their dog. The novelist depicts the trials with wit and a wry narrative voice that ensures a half-laugh on every page. In this novella, Madhusudan Sen, the main character, is so consumed with revenge that he is unable to extend pity to anyone, not even someone who served 23 years in prison for an act of rage. This study intends to interpret legal systems through literature in which the author depicts the slowness of the judicial system and prejudiced moralities regarding meat. He juxtaposes violent or traumatic events with bleak comedy and questions the readers' values and perceptions. This study appeals not only to scholars, but also to all readers and teachers of law and literature.

Keywords: Trials, Fiction, revenge, murder, non-vegetarian food, Judicial system, existential crisis.

Any creative work that portrays fictional people, events, and locations in an imaginative manner is considered to be fiction. Fiction can take many forms. It is a symbol of how an author manipulates, concentrates, and alters reality in order to tell a story. Fiction refers to narratives written in prose, including novels, novellas, and short stories. Typically, a trial scene is included in legal fiction. Literature has always been filled with a fascination for trials. The purpose of a trial is to seek for the truth. The reality is that many individuals find actual trials to be tedious. In most cases, the real trials aren't quite as exciting as the ones that are depicted in fiction.

The 1995 legal thriller *The Rainmaker* by American author John Grisham is an excellent example. It is the story of a young lawyer fresh out of law school who takes on one of America's most powerful, corrupt, and vicious companies and exposes a multibillion-dollar insurance scam.

The Firm, his second book, released in 1991, is also a legal thriller that achieved widespread success. It is the story of how a bright and ambitious Harvard-educated attorney ends up working for a mafia-owned legal practice. He discovers that the administration does not permit anyone to leave the organisation alive. He goes about his normal business while secretly carrying out undercover operations against his bosses and simultaneously formulating a strategy for his escape.

Presumed Innocent is the 1987 novel by Scott Turow about a prosecutor accused of murdering his colleague, Carolyn Polhemus, an attractive and brilliant prosecutor. It dives extensively into the character of the accused, a high-ranking assistant district attorney on trial for the murder of a colleague with whom he had an affair.

To Kill a Mockingbird is the 1960 novel by Harper Lee which centres on Atticus Finch's defence of Tom Robinson, a black man who is suspected of having sexually assaulted a white lady, and the events that unfold during the trial. It was awarded the Pulitzer Prize.

Upamanyu Chatterjee's seventh work, the novella *The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian*, recounts the trials in a very realistic manner. These trials highlight the evils of modern India, such as class discrepancies, prejudiced moralities regarding meat, and the sluggishness of the Judicial system.

Within the realm of Indian literature written in the English language, Upamanyu Chatterjee has quickly established himself as one of the most fascinating emerging voices. He is best known for his writings set in the Indian Administrative Service, namely *English, August: An Indian Story* and its sequel *The Mammaries of the Welfare State*. On December 19, 1959, he was born into a Hindu Bengali Brahmin family in Patna, Bihar. He received his elementary and secondary education at St.

Xavier's School, Delhi, and his master's degree in English literature from St. Stephen's College, Delhi.

In 1983, Upamanyu Chatterjee entered the prestigious Indian Administrative Service from the Maharashtra cadre. It served as the foundation for his creative career, from which he drew inspiration for his marvellous characters. In 1990, he was a writer-in-residence at Kent University in the United Kingdom. In 1998, he was appointed Director of Languages for the Ministry of Human Resource Development of India. Since March 2009, he has served as a Joint secretary in the Ministry of Defense. Until March 20, 2016, he also served as Secretary of the Petroleum and Natural Gas Regulatory Board (PNGRB). He was blessed with two daughters, Sara and Pia, after marrying Anne, a French journalist.

When Chatterjee was still in high school, he penned a play that was based on a plot from the Alfred Hitchcock movie *Dilemma*. In spite of the fact that it parodied the school's policies and procedures, it was awarded first place in the theatre competition. He is the author of six different novels. They are *English, August: An Indian Story* (1988), *The Last Burden* (1993), *The Mammaries of the Welfare State* (2000), *Weight Loss* (2006), *Way to Go* (2010), and *Fairy Tales at Fifty* (2014). He has authored several short stories, *The Assassination of Indira Gandhi* (1986) and *Watching Them*. He received the Sahitya Akademi Award for *The Mammaries of the Welfare State* (2000), a sequel to *English, August: An Indian Story*. Chatterjee received the coveted *Officier des Arts et des Lettres* award from the French government in 2008 for his contributions to contemporary literature.

The present paper tries to explore the realistic depiction of trials in Indian English novels like *The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian* by Chatterjee. The storyline of the novella *The Revenge of the Non-vegetarian* is a straightforward narrative in which a family of six and their dog perish in a fire where "the flames had swallowed up the entire single-storey building and rose, with a frightful rustle and roar, fifteen feet in the air" in Batia, Narmada Pradesh (*The Revenge of the Non-Vegetarian* 10). Even though the story takes place between 1949 and 1973, it is ageless and yet relevant today.

According to what the title says, it appears to be the act of vengeance carried out by a non-vegetarian named Madhusudan, ICS against another non-vegetarian named Basant Kumar Bal for the murder of Nadim Dalvi's entire family. It is also the servant Basant's retaliation against his lord for depriving him of the means to sustain himself. It begins with a murder inquiry and progresses to beef politics, letting the reader to contemplate his own biases. Madhusudhan Sen, an ICS official, is the Sub-divisional Magistrate of Batia and a non-vegetarian cuisine enthusiast whose average breakfast in Calcutta consists of "eggs and sausages, liver, toast, fruit, and tea" (*TRNV* 28). Madhusudan appears to be more tolerant than Agastya Sen, Madhusudan Sen's son, whom the reader encountered in Chatterjee's debut novel *English August: An Indian Story*. He tells his muslim mamlatdar Nadeem Dalvi, "well, frankly, I like the bungalow that's been allotted to me, those centurial trees, those arches, that picturesque well" (*TRNV* 35).

Madhusudan Sen resides in a "rather charming late-nineteenth-century bungalow on Temple Road in the Civil Lines area" that is part of an unofficial no-meat zone due to its proximity to the Dayasagar Adinath Temple, which is revered by the local community (*TRNV* 25). However, he devises a technique to obtain a non-vegetarian evening meal through his mamlatdar. Food creates an odd friendship between these two individuals. As food is the core focus of the book, the author covers a number of significant issues, such as beef politics and cow vigilantism. Every day, after leaving the magistrate's court, Sen makes his way back to his bungalow in Civil Lines, where he then enjoys a drink of Cutty Sark whisky and a Gold Flake cigarette. In a provincial posting, he leads a mundane bureaucratic existence surrounded by punkhahs, peons, and other eavesdropping employees.

Dalvi resides in a massive home with his family and a dog. Basant Kumar Bal is Dalvi's servant who resides in the outhouse and performs all home tasks, including "ferrying in water and wood and coal, washing up, rushing to the bazaar to buy sugar and eggs, tending to the cows, clearing the clothesline... Never a moment's rest for him" (*TRNV* 18). Although Bal resides in Batia, he is a

native of Purulia, a region he left “some twelve years ago” after his mother’s death, and he has no family there (*TRNV 74*).

During the course of the investigation, when Basant Kumar Bal was questioned about his employers, he stated that his bosses “always ate well” (*TRNV 19*) and that “they had non-vegetarian almost every day, saab, goat or chicken or fish or egg” (*TRNV 20*). They gorged themselves like rakshasas and never left more than two small pieces of meat in the stew, one each for the sister-in-law and her daughter. Every night, after the rest of the Dalvi family has gone to bed, Bal “had his dinner in the shed, whatever was left over for him by the sister-in-law and her daughter [who were treated like servants in the Dalvi house-hold] from whatever had been left over for them” (*TRNV 19*). The only thing that Bal was able to salvage for his supper were “the scrapings of the pot, some gobs of curry, some grains of rice and a couple of chapatis ... have to filch two green chillis and one raw onion to complete” his meal (*TRNV 20*). As he was not even provided with sufficient food, he murders Nadeem Dalvi and his family out of rage and sets their home on fire, “destroying life and property in the most inhumanly cruel manner” (*TRNV 65*).

As Bal murders Nadeem Dalvi’s family for meat, an enraged Sen begins to investigate the loss of his supplier of “principal protein and cholesterol” and promises to become a vegetarian until justice is served (*TRNV 39*). In addition, he used the letter of the law to shut down an illegal slaughterhouse, which he was unaware of until he happened to come across its terrible odour during one of his road journeys. This made the entire village of Batia to become vegetarian. The author describes the current state of religious intolerance in our country, in which Muslims and beef eaters are persecuted. When Basant Kumar was brought to court, the Honorable Magistrate explains the long, complicated criminal proceedings and sarcastically remarks:

The court clerk will inform you now of the procedure relating to criminal proceedings, the FIR, the Investigating Officer’s Report, then you will appear before a Judicial Magistrate who will take cognizance of the crime, a charge sheet would be prepared, you’d have to spend some time in judicial custody in prison awaiting trial, and the hearing itself in the court of sessions- all that you may expect in the days- I should say years-to come. (*TRNV 69-70*)

Basant entered Narasinh Nagar’s primary jail on “October 21, 1949 and stayed there, in the first phase, for four years, six months and eleven days” while awaiting trial (*TRNV 72*). In detention, Basant was counselled to “plead Not Guilty ... cops terrorized you into signing that confession ... Plead temporary insanity ... You hadn’t had meat for so long that something snapped in your head. Then you might get life. Life in jail, you’ll agree, is better than death” (*TRNV 74*). The court appointed him an attorney.

When Bal was ordered to appear in court, he found himself in an unfamiliar and unsafe environment outside of the prison. The author satirizes the media by comparing journalists to “stray dogs about to attack a cur who has wandered into their territory” (*TRNV 76-77*). In the moments leading up to the trial, “a tall, thin, balding man in an advocate’s dress accosted him amidst the din and the jostle to bark into his ear, ‘We will plead Not Guilty’” and if someone asks about the fire “you will say you were sleeping. You don’t know who did it” (*TRNV 77*).

Bal returns to prison “in the late afternoon exhausted and afraid, less of death somehow than of living...” following the trial. (*TRNV 77*). The author tries to describe the predicament of modern man, who is more afraid of living than of dying. One can observe the same, “gaze of the unstable temperament” on Bal’s face even after twenty-one years (*TRNV 113*). He is unable to discover the meaning or purpose of his existence. This results in modern man’s existential crises. Rekha K and Dr Rama N. H. Alapati in their article “Almost ridiculous: Dark humour in Upamanyu Chatterjee’s *The Revenge of the Non-vegetarian*” rightly say that the predicament of modern man “reflects the central dilemma of black humor novels i.e., the terror of existing without reason, of wandering in the postmodern chaos” (46). The death row inmate Bal in the story, who is unconcerned with what happens outside the prison walls or whether anyone remembers him or not as he is “not that kind of human being,” is compared to the unfortunate animals that grow up in closed confines without ever

having seen the outside world or knowing what it is like to be in the open (*TRNV* 74). His existential conundrum is a result of his distanced viewpoint and identity conflict.

Basant spent the remaining 17 years of his life at the Narsinh Nagar Central prison. He was incarcerated alongside three other inmates who referred to him as Gomaas Kumar since they were all vegetarians. They were friendly to him and informed him about the delay in court processes, where “judges take so long to examine and take stock that it gives potatoes and other tubers enough time to grow between their Honourable toes” (*TRNV* 103-104).

In addition to this, they claim that attorneys are filthier than the faeces of a non-vegetarian because “they suck you dry of whatever money you have” (*TRNV* 104). When Bal submits his petition for Special Leave to the Supreme Court, one of the other inmates says, you may sit and “relax and masturbate for the next four years, give or take another five” (*TRNV* 106). Also, he states that the Supreme Court will not be moved to tears by your wailing so, if “I am around, we shall draft a mercy petition to the President of India,” who never says die (*TRNV* 106). The trials and sluggishness of the judicial system are shown in a manner that is very true to life by the author.

In one occasion, a death row inmate seeking clemency writes to King George VI rather than the President. Upon questioning the subordinate informs the Inspector General, “That’s the template, sir, used by several dozen prisoners ever since the forties”, and “it will serve its purpose, sir” (*TRNV* 111). No matter how serious the subject matter, the author approaches it from a comic perspective. As Scholes contends, the Black humorist “seeks rather a comic perspective on both tragic fact and moralistic certitude” (Schulz 13).

After the trial, on February 7, 1956, Judge Shyamlal ruled that “heartless and satanic” Bal, who sat among the bodies to eat their non-vegetarian dinner, “is to be hanged by the neck till he is dead” (*TRNV* 98). Chatterjee compares the killing of animals for food to the death of humans as a kind of punishment. Sen, pondering the legitimacy of the death sentence, ponders whether vegetarians view the death penalty as an appropriate punishment. He asks Mr. Daftari, for instance, would all vegetarians “be opposed to the death penalty for even the most despicable murderer?” (*TRNV* 89). If the death penalty is permissible, why isn’t the killing of animals for food acceptable to vegetarians? Likewise, if the death penalty is not acceptable, why is the killing of animals acceptable to non-vegetarians?

The author makes the following observation while discussing the delays that occur within the judicial system: “Justice delayed is justice denied; true, but justice delayed for twenty-one years is also a gift of two decades of life to a recipient unworthy of even a moment of it” (*TRNV* 110). Sen reads the telex announcing the President’s decision to commute Basant’s death sentence to life in prison. He gently “tears the letter off the machine, all the while murmuring to himself, absentmindedly, a sort of refrain: ‘The quality of justice is not strained, the-quality-of-justice-is-not-strained’” (*TRNV* 124). He reorganises the paper on the machine such that it appears as if “the order was never received.” Back in his room, he drinks his “horrible tea,” and on the way home, he stops briefly at “Qayamat’s for a minute to pick up some kebabs” (*TRNV* 124). The activities of Sen that may have led to the execution of the servant leave the reader in a moral quandary.

Using humour and a realistic depiction of court proceedings, Upamanyu Chatterjee deftly presents religious and political issues and describes how a powerful, high-caste man avenged the death of another affluent man by killing a person he viewed as inferior. What appeared to be non-vegetarian retribution is actually privileged retribution. After becoming a vegetarian, Sen forces the entire town of Batia to follow suit by closing the abattoirs at the recommendation of a member of the temple trust, so limiting the dietary freedom of others. The novel sheds attention on the inequality between those who have and those who do not as the murder is committed for the purpose of obtaining the non-vegetarian soup that the killer, Basanth Kumar, craves for.

References

- Chatterjee, Upamanyu. *The Revenge of the Non-vegetarian*. Speaking Tiger, 2018. Print.
- Rekha, K, and Dr. Rama N.H. Alapati. "Almost ridiculous: Dark humour in Upamanyu Chatterjee's *The Revenge of the Non-vegetarian*." *International Journal of English: Literature, Language & Skills*, vol. 10, no. 3, October 2021, pp. 44-48. Print.
- Schulz, Max. *Black Humor Fiction of the Sixties: A Pluralistic Definition of Man and His World*. Ohio UP, 1973. Print.